

Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices of Nurses in the Tamale Metropolis Towards Coronavirus Prevention

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Abstract – The coronavirus pandemic that engulfed the world continues to bring health care facilities and personnel including nurses to their knees. Both human and material resources are overburdened, cost of personal protective equipment have soar up amidst high demand. Nevertheless, nurses continue to play the frontline role to aid in dealing with the pandemic. This exposes them to contracting the virus therefore making it essential for nurses to acquaint themselves with high level of knowledge and prevention practices to stay safe to continue to render care to patients. The study explored the nurses' knowledge, attitude and practices towards coronavirus prevention. A quantitative descriptive study design was adopted for the work to gather data on knowledge, attitude and practices. Data was collected from 196 nurses/midwives using a self-administered questionnaire. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and results presented in the form of frequency tables and percentages and figures. The attitude of the nurses/midwives can generally be considered to be good with good prevention practices that can be associated with their educational qualification, working experience and motivational levels. It can be concluded that the nurses and midwives had adequate knowledge regarding coronavirus (SARS-CoV 2).

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Practices, Coronavirus, Nurse

1. INTRODUCTION

The spread of an infection that is related to the health sector continues to be a public health concern in many parts of the world. This has led to an increase in cost, morbidity and mortality in every facet of the health sector and its settings (Mauldin et al, 2010). In recent times, there have been many discussions on the transmission of coronaviruses. Coronaviruses are a group or family of viruses that causes illnesses emanating from a common cold to more severe diseases such as the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory syndrome (SARS). Of recent addition is a novel coronavirus that has been isolated and named COVID-19 (WHO, 2020).

The new coronavirus was discovered in China in December, 2019 and there has been global spread from human to human which has taken a lot of lives and brought more strain on health care facilities and the economies of all countries affected including Ghana. As at April 30, 2020, the total number of confirmed positive cases worldwide stood at 7,039,918 with 404,396 deaths affecting 215 countries globally and 11,946 positive cases recorded in Ghana with the Northern region of which Tamale is the capital recording 37 positive cases (WHO, Coronavirus Disease 2019 Update as at June 13, 2020; GHS, 2020).

There is therefore the need to get a better understanding of the knowledge, attitude and practices of nurses regarding the prevention of the

coronavirus. Among other measures instituted and recommended by the World Health Organization together with its agencies includes regular hand hygiene, social distancing, wearing of face mask and others.

1.2 Problem Statement

There has been a growing concern regarding the spread of coronavirus across the African continent and for that matter Ghana considering the nature and set up of Ghana's public places thus; markets, churches, mosques and institutional facilities because most of these places do not make provision for hand wand washing or sanitizing.

Currently, there has not been any vaccine or specific treatment plan for MERS CoV, SARS CoV and Covid-19. Therefore, applying preventive measures to reduce the spread of the disease is of the utmost importance (Al-Hazmi et al, 2018). The WHO and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) have published recommendations for the prevention and control of MERS infection in health care settings (de Groot et al, 2013) and recently COVID-19. These include hand hygiene, wearing personal protective equipment, and patient isolation, social distancing and others ((WHO), 2020; (CDC), 2015).

Globally, several nations have made strives and instituted certain restrictions and guidelines to reduce or stop the spread through closing of ports and borders, mandatory quarantine and self-isolation, compulsory use of face mask, regular hand washing and sanitizing among others. Notwithstanding these, the effects of this current novel COVID-19 pandemic has largely been negative to the world's economy affecting all sectors worldwide and this will go down in history as one of the worst pandemics to hit the world. China's initial response to contain the virus has been applauded by the WHO and considered much improved compared with its response to the 2003 SARS-CoV epidemic. Internationally, there has been rapid generation and sharing of knowledge to the benefit of the pandemic response, but also counterproductive actions by some countries, including limiting trade and shutting of borders, to its detriment. With the increasing frequency of human to human transmission of the infection, it is apparent that pandemic preparedness has become a priority for the global health agenda of which nurses play a vital role. Based on the study problem, the reason for this study aims to examine the knowledge,

attitude and practices of nurses regarding the prevention of COVID-19 using nurses in the Tamale Metropolis of the Northern Region as a case study.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to explore the nurses' knowledge, attitude and practices regarding the prevention of coronavirus (COVI-19) in the Tamale Metropolis.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the study will;

- Examine the knowledge of the nurses regarding coronavirus (COVID-19) and its prevention
- Explore the attitude of the nurses towards the prevention of COVID-19
- Determine the practices of the nurse in the prevention of the spread of COVID-19
- Make recommendations to improve the knowledge, attitude and practices on the prevention of COVID-19

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Knowledge of Coronavirus Prevention

Alsaifi and Cheng (2016) conducted a study on knowledge, attitude and behaviors of healthcare workers in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to MERS Coronavirus and other emerging infectious diseases of which more than half of their participants (56.5%) were nurses. The result of the study revealed that the frequent source where they got MERS-CoV information among the healthcare workers was from the Ministry of Health memos with 30.4% of the nurses knowing that some patients with coronavirus could be asymptomatic (Alsaifi and Cheng, 2016). It concluded that the knowledge of the healthcare workers was poor on new diseases, hence, training and educating the healthcare workers on how to use personal protective equipment, patient management and measures to prevent spread (Alsaifi and Cheng, 2016).

Ebrahimi and Nemati (2020), in a study that measured the level of nurses' awareness during the current outbreak of COVID-19 in Shiraz, Iran showed that little over 50% of the nurses were aware of the transmission mode, early signs and symptoms, treatment outcomes and the level of mortality of COVID-19 in Iran. Similarly, most of the nurses had their sources of information to

be the World Health Organisations's website and Iran's MoH regular updates. Less than half of the participants had their sources from the media and other social applications (Ebrahimi and Nemati 2020). The results further showed that more than half of the nurses had worked for more than 5 years and knew other families of coronavirus before the outbreak of COVID-19 (Ebrahimi and Nemati 2020).

A qualitative study was conducted in China to ascertain healthcare personnel's experience in the crisis of the COVID-19. The study showed that nurses had a key and very important role to play in providing care at intensive care units and helping in the activity of daily living of patients. The healthcare workers had to adjust to a new challenge of the increasing workload due to higher numbers of patients being infected. The study concluded that the intensive work made healthcare providers physically and emotionally exhausted and recommended a regular and intensive training for them to promote their preparedness and efficacy in managing crisis (Liu et al, 2020).

Huynh et al, (2020), assessed the knowledge of healthcare workers at District 2 hospital in Ho, Minh City. The findings revealed a good knowledge by the healthcare workers, however only 2/3 knew how COVID-19 is spread, the treatment options and quarantine/ isolation procedures. The level of knowledge of some of the participants did not correspond to their rank or placement in the healthcare setting. Most of the participants knew the causative organism of covid-19 (Huynh et al, 2020).

Zhou et al, (2020), in a study at Henan, China, also assessed healthcare workers' knowledge in nurses and found adequate knowledge among the participants regarding COVID-19 even though medical doctors recorded higher knowledge level than nurses. However, the participants feared the risk of being infected. The study concluded that steps be taken to safeguard the healthcare workers at all levels. (Zhou et al, 2020).

A study involving psychiatric medical staff in China which included 170 mental health nurses evaluated their knowledge and attitudes regarding the COVID-19 epidemic; there was a higher knowledge among all the participants with majority receiving adequate training on the care of patients infected with COVID-19. The participants were self-motivated to care for patients with

mental illness who have tested positive for the virus (Shi et al, 2020).

Al-Hazmi et al, (2018), in a cross-sectional study conducted among students from different schools in Riyadh determined the attitudes and knowledge of students. Their knowledge scores were not significantly different with most of them citing exposure to coughing, sneezing and heavily crowded areas as common sources of getting infected as well as touching or handling of infected surfaces. The participants also noted there is high interest of citizens to get first-hand information on how to take measures that will protect them at homes and in public places and recommended that premium be placed on preventive methods education. The general knowledge was high among female participants compared to their male counterparts and most of them noted fever and difficulty breathing as symptoms (Al-Hazmi et al, 2018).

Erfani et al, (2020), conducted a survey using a specific population in Iran to assess their practices, attitude and knowledge towards COVID-19 in Iran. The study depicted a high score in the knowledge level on the characteristics of the disease, persons or groups who are at a higher risk and how the disease is transmitted. Different age groups, the level of education of participants, age and their marital status influenced the level of knowledge (Erfani et al, 2020).

Kumar et al, (2020), conducted a study in Pakistan to examine nurses' knowledge, attitude and practices regarding the use of face mask in limiting the spread of COVID-19 using an interview to collect data. The findings of the study showed an understanding of the right method of using a surgical mask, duration it has to be worn as well as the effectiveness of a standard surgical mask versus the use of a cloth mask and the correct way of disposing it off.

2.2 Attitudes towards Coronavirus Infection Transmission and Prevention

In a study conducted by Erfani et al, (2020), using specific population in Iran to examine their knowledge, attitude and practice towards COVID-19 in Iran. The study found a positive attitude among the participants towards the COVID-19 pandemic in Iran that was also different among individuals. The low level of education of participants and those who resided in larger

households had decrease in attitude (Erfani et al, 2020).

Saqlain et al, (2020), in their study in Pakistan depicted a generally good attitude by healthcare workers towards COVID-19. The participants noted that, the use of PPE and managing infected patients in isolation will help prevent the transmission of infection. The healthcare workers suggested greatly that being more knowledgeable about COVID-19 by taking part in infection prevention control programs will boost their attitude towards COVID-19 (Saqlain et al, 2020).

Giao et al, (2020) in their study at District 2 hospital, Ho Chi Minh City, reported a good attitude among the health workers. The healthcare workers also showed concern about themselves and their relatives getting infected. The participant showed their readiness to be quarantined should any of them contract COVID-19. They however, noted that the best method of prevention is regular hand hygiene (Giao et al, 2020).

Alsahafi and Cheng (2016), in their study, assessed the attitude and behaviors of health workers towards MERS-CoV in Saudi Arabia, found out that the workers were willing to use the preventive guidelines issued by policy directors during the outbreak. However, the study found poor attitude towards handwashing/sanitizing, lack of infection prevention and control protocols and inadequate training organised for the healthcare workers contributed to an increased risk level of the participants (Alsahafi and Cheng, 2016).

Asaad et al, (2020), examined the knowledge and attitude among healthworkers towards MERS in Saudi Arabia. The study found out that majority of healthcare workers have good attitude in the area of infection prevention and control guidelines and programmes designed. The participants noted that, it is the surest way to combat the pandemic, however, they showed a poor attitude towards the search for vaccines (Asaad et al, 2020).

Zhou et al, (2020), in their study at Henan, China assessed the practices, knowledge and attitudes of COVID-19 with almost half of the participants being nurses showed that the health workers' experience and category had influence on their attitudes toward COVID-19 as well as their knowledge level. The higher the level of knowledge, the more they showed a positive attitude. The healthcare workers were concerned about being stressed up and expressed the

possibility of being infected (Zhou et al, 2020). Similarly, Shi et al, (2020), found in their study among medical staff in a psychiatric hospital that the level of confidence of the psychiatrist in protecting themselves and others was higher than that of the nurses even though they showed their readiness to help and support and care for patients with COVID-19 (Shi et al, 2020).

2.3 Practices towards the Prevention of Coronavirus

Kumar et al, (2020), in their study that examined nurses' knowledge, attitude and practices regarding the use of face mask in limiting the spread of COVID-19 revealed the nurses mostly do not take off their face mask when they need to speak to a patient. They do not also reuse the surgical mask; however, they wear a mask when they move within or around the hospital and at public places to prevent them from contacting the infection.

An online research carried out by Rahman and Sathi (2020) among internet users in Bangladeshi regarding the knowledge, attitude and COVID-19 preventive practices depicted that most of the participants noted the use of facemask, observing social distancing, sanitizing of hands or hand hygiene and staying home as some of the preventive practices they observe (Rahman and Sathi, 2020). A similar study was undertaken by Lihua et al, (2020), which concluded that there is the need to encourage regular disinfection of surfaces and handles with alcohol or chlorine and regular handwashing before and after eating.

Erfani et al, (2020), noted in their study that participants had an average COVID-19 practice score which varied depending on their marital status, gender, age and the number of persons they lived with as well as the level of education. This has been related to a probable good practice with a high knowledge level of the participants. The study therefore concluded that, participants showed appropriate prevention practices towards COVID-19. Related findings were observed by Saqlain et al, (2020), where the participants demonstrated good practices associated with working experience, age and gender. They however identified inadequate knowledge in the disease transmission and preventive protocols as hindrances to the practices (Saqlain et al, 2020).

The findings from the research conducted by Alsahafi and Cheng (2016), reported self-preventive practices by the healthcare workers.

More than half of the nurses and physicians washed their hands after patient contact. On the contrary, less than half of the participants adhered to the use of facemask when necessary. The participants enumerated lack of PPEs, crowded wards, the absence infection prevention protocols and hand washing points as barriers to complying the preventive practices (Alsahafi and Cheng, 2016).

Tadese and Demoz (2020), also rated the practices of nurses in Ethiopia towards COVID-19 as good in a study that assessed their knowledge, attitude, practice and psychological response during the pandemic of COVID-19.

Alfahan et al, (2016), conducted a study among health care professionals to assess their compliance with hand hygiene in the period of coronavirus. The participants noted that they regularly perform handrub with alcohol and frequent hand washing in the midst of work overload. The practices of hand hygiene were not affected by their colleagues who did not comply with hand hygiene protocols. The participants called for an increased supply of hand sanitizers to boost their practices. Their working experience and level of training had a direct influence on their hand hygiene practices (Alfahan et al, 2016).

As a general practice in the prevention of the spread of COVID-19, the WHO (2020), offered and published certain guidelines to ensure compliance. Notable is frequent washing of hand using soap under running water for at least 20-40 seconds. This will ensure that the number of resident microorganisms are drastically reduced. WHO also has strongly advocated for the use of hand-rubs made from alcohol based agents in the absence of items needed to wash hands and observing a respectable distance, covering of the mouth and nose when coughing or sneezing and properly disposing off used tissues (WHO, 2020).

In Kenya, Olum et al, (2020), researched into healthcare workers' knowledge, attitude and practices regarding COVID-19. The study found most participants used facemask and washed their hands when they carry out a procedure on patients. Most participants refrained from going closer to patients who exhibited signs of COVID-19. Also, the study reported better practices among participants who attained a higher level of education and training (Olum et al, 2020).

3. RESEARCH METHODS

A quantitative descriptive study design was adopted for the work to gather data on the knowledge, attitude and practices of the nurses towards coronavirus. A self-administered closed and open ended questions was used to answer the research questions.

The target population for the study were all the nurses who were accessible and were voluntarily given consent to take part in the study. Tamale Central Hospital and the Tamale Teaching Hospital were the hospitals used for the study

Using a margin of error (5%) and a confidence interval of 95% (1.96), the formula below (Cochran's formula) was used to calculate the minimum number of sample size that was used for the study:

$$N_o = \frac{Z^2pq}{e^2}$$

Where:

e is margin of error

p is estimated proportion of participants

q is 1-p

Z is the confidence interval

Substituting the values:

$$N_o = \frac{(1.96)^2 x (0.85)(1 - 0.85)}{0.05^2}$$

$$N_o = \frac{3.84 x 0.85 x 0.15}{0.0025}$$

$$N_o = \frac{0.4896}{0.0025}$$

$$N_o = 195.8$$

The minimum sample size required for the study is approximately 196 participants.

Only registered nurses who were at post were included in the study except ward in-charges rotation nurses, trainees and nurses on study leave, maternity leave and sick leaves.

Self-administered questionnaire was used to obtain data from the nurses and was analyzed and presented in the form of frequency tables using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS version 22).

4. DATA ANALYSIS

The study explored the nurses' knowledge, attitude and practices regarding the prevention of

coronavirus (COVID-19). The analysis of the research data was done using SPSS version 22. Findings from the analysis have been presented in the form of frequency tables and charts or figures.

4.1 Bio-Demographic Data of Respondents

This section presents the findings of the analysis of the bio-demographic data of respondents of the study.

Table 1: Age of Respondents

Age (years)	Frequency	Percentage
20-30	93	47.5
31-40	91	46.4
41-50	8	4.1
Above 50 years	4	2.0
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

From table 1, 93(47.5%) of the respondents were between the ages 20-30 years, 91(46.4%) were between 31-40years, 8(4.1%) aged 41-50 years with only 4(2%) being above 50years.

From figure 1, majority of the respondents 118(60.2%) were males whilst 78(39.8%) were females.

Figure 1: Gender of Respondents

Table 2: Respondents' Place of Work

Work place	Frequency	Percentage
Tamale Teaching Hospital	125	63.8
Tamale Central Hospital	71	36.2
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Majority of the respondents, 125(63.8%) worked at the Tamale Teaching Hospital and 71(36.2%) work at the Tamale Central Hospital. This is shown in table 2.

It can be seen from figure 2 that, 66(33.7%) of the respondents worked at the female medical ward, 39(19.9%) worked at the male medical ward, 20(10.2%) worked at the general surgery unit, 16(8.2%) respectively worked at the pediatric ward and the accident/emergency unit, 15(7.7%) works at the antenatal clinic, 12(6.1%) works at the OPD whilst 9(4.6%) works at the maternity ward with only 3(1.5%) working at the labor ward.

Figure 2: Unit/Ward of Respondents

Table 3: Category of Respondents

Category of Nurse	Frequency	Percentage
RN	129	65.8
RM	9	4.6
NAC	46	23.5
NAP	9	4.6
Others	3	1.5
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

As indicated in table 3, more than half, 129(65.8%) of the respondents were registered nurses, 46(23.5%) were nurse assistant clinical, 9(4.6%) respectively were registered midwives and nurse assistant preventive whilst 3(1.5%) were in the other categories.

Table 4: Rank of Respondents

Rank	Frequency	Percentage
EN	46	23.5
SN/SM	29	14.8
SSN/SSM	54	27.6
NO/MO	33	16.8
SNO	15	7.6
PNO	10	5.1
CHN	9	4.6
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Most of the respondents 54(27.6%) were senior staff nurse/midwife, 46(23.5%) were enrolled nurses, 33(16.8%) were nursing/midwifery officers, 15(7.6%) were senior nursing officers whilst 10(5.1%) were principal nursing officers and 9(4.6%) being community health nurses. This is depicted in table 4.

Table 5: Respondents' Working Experience

Work Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	100	51.1
6-10	72	36.7
11-15	20	10.2
Above 15 years	4	2.0
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

From table 5, 100(51.1%) of the respondents had working experience between 1-5years, 72(36.7%) had a working experience between 6-10 years, 20(10.2%) between 11-15years whilst 4(2.0%) worked for more than 15 years.

Table 6: Marital Status of Respondents.

Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	61	31.1
Single	129	65.8
Widow(er)	3	1.5
Divorced	3	1.5
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

More than half, 129(65.8%) are single, 61(31.2%) are married with 3(1.5%) being widows or widowers and divorced respectively. This is shown in table 6.

As indicated in figure 3, 102(52%) of the respondents have diploma in nursing/midwifery, 48(24.5%) have certificate in nurse assistant clinical/preventive, 40(20.4%) have bachelor's degree whilst 6(3.1%) have postgraduate degree.

Figure 3: Level of Education of Respondents

4.2 Knowledge Level of Respondents Regarding Coronavirus (SARS-CoV 2)

This section assessed the level of the respondents' knowledge on Coronavirus.

Close to half, 95(48.5%) of the respondents first heard about COVID-19 in December, 2019, 68(34.7%) first heard of COVID-19 in February, 2020 whilst 33(16.8%) heard more of COVID-19 in March, 2020. This is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Information about COVID-19

Majority of the respondents, 110(56.1%) used the television as their primary source of information on COVID-19, 44(22.4%) use the radio, 16(8.2%) use social media handles of relevant agencies, 10(5.1%) use reports from the GHS/MoH whilst 7(3.6%) relied on information from colleagues and 6(3.1%) use workshop materials and 3(1.5%)

use the internet to search for information on COVID-19. This is depicted in figure 5.

Figure 5: Source of Information on COVID-19

Table 7: Knowledge about Coronavirus

Statement	Response	
	Yes	No
COVID-19 can be caused by an organism called coronavirus	170(86.7%)	26(13.3%)
COVID-19 can be spread from human to human	196(100%)	0(0)
Health workers including nurses are at a higher risk of getting infected	196(100%)	0(0)
The virus has an incubation period of 2-14 days	193(98.5%)	3(1.5%)
Difficulty breathing, sore throat, fever, coughing and runny nose are possible symptoms of COVID-19	196(100%)	0(0)
Infected persons above 60 years are at risk of COVID-19 complications	193(98.5%)	3(1.5%)
Infected persons with chronic heart problems, hypertension, diabetes and other comorbidities have a high mortality rate	179(91.3%)	17(8.7%)
There is a specific treatment regimen for COVID-19	54(27.6%)	142(72.4%)
There is a vaccine against COVID-19	34(17.3%)	162(82.7%)
Very close contact with infected persons can transmit the infection	187(95.4%)	9(4.6%)
Quarantining or isolation of patients is used in the management of COVID-19	175(89.3%)	21(10.7%)
Persons who do not exhibit symptoms cannot transmit the virus	124(63.3%)	72(36.7%)
COVID-19 affects persons at all ages	187(95.4%)	9(4.6%)
Overcrowded areas can be a source of infection	196(100%)	0(0)
Touching or handling of infected surfaces and items can be a source of infection	196(100%)	0(0)
Wearing of facemask and regular hand washing prevents the spread of the virus	192(98%)	4(2%)

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Similarly, 179(91.3%) of the respondents noted that infected persons with chronic heart problems, hypertension, diabetes and other comorbidities have a high mortality rate whilst 17(8.7%) responded negative, 54(27.6%) indicated that there is a specific treatment for COVID-19 and majority, 142(72.4%) indicating there is no specific treatment regimen. Also, 34(17.3%) indicated the presence of a vaccine for COVID-19 whilst 162(82.7%) noted there is currently no vaccine. Transmission of the infection through close contact and COVID 19 affecting all ages

Data analyzed and presented in table 7 shows that, 170(86.7%) of the respondents indicated COVID-19 is caused by the coronavirus (SARS CoV 2) whilst 26(13.3%) answered negative, all the respondents, 196(100%) respectively noted that the virus can be spread from human to human and health workers including nurses being at a higher risk of getting infected with difficulty in breathing, sore throat, fever, coughing and runny nose being possible symptoms of COVID-19. Majority 193(98.5%) respectively also indicated that SARS CoV 2 has incubation period between 2 to 14 days and infected persons above 60 years are at risk of COVID-19 complications with 3(1.5%) answering otherwise.

infection. Wearing of face mask and regular hand washing prevents the spread of the virus was also stated by 192(98%) whilst only 4(2%) indicated otherwise.

Table 8: Respondents Attitude towards COVID-19 Prevention

Statement	Response	
	Yes	No
I am ready to attend COVID-19 training programs	196(100%)	0(0)
I fear my relatives may get infected	171(87.2%)	25(12.8%)
I will accept to be quarantined should I contract COVID-19 as a nurse	193(98.5%)	3(1.5%)
I always use preventive guidelines designed by health agencies	193(98.5%)	3(1.5%)
I am confident in my ability to help in the fight against COVID-19	196(100%)	0(0)
Increased workload affects my work attitude	144(73.5%)	52(26.5%)
I use my working experience in the area of COVID-19 preventions	193(98.5%)	3(1.5%)
I don PPE properly before I attend to patients	147(75%)	49(25%)
I am ready to give education on COVID-19	196(100%)	0(0)
I am self-motivated to go to work every day in this pandemic	174(88.8%)	22(11.2%)

Source: Field Survey, 2020

All the respondents, 196(100%) indicated their readiness to attend COVID-19 training programs, with confidence to fight against COVID-19 and the willingness to give education on COVID-19. 171(87.2%) feared their relatives may get infected whilst 25(12.8%) did not fear, 193(98.5%) respectively will accept to be quarantined should they contract the disease, use their working experience in the area of COVID-19 prevention and agreed to use the preventive guidelines designed by health agencies whilst 3(1.5%) respectively will not accept to be quarantined or follow the health agencies designed guidelines and use their working experience. 144(73.5%) responded that increased workload affects their work attitude towards COVID-19 while 52(26.5%) noted otherwise, 147(75%) don PPE properly before they attend to patients with 49(25%) unable to don PPE properly and 174(88.8%) of the respondents are self-motivated to go to work every day in this pandemic whilst 22(11.2%) are not self-motivated to go to work. Details are indicated in table 8.

4.3 Attitudes toward Covid-19 Prevention

This section also examined the attitudes of the respondents in relation to the prevention of COVID-19.

4.4 Practices towards COVID-19 Prevention

The practices of respondents towards the prevention of COVID-19 were examined in this section.

Table 9: Hand washing with soap and water

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Always	156	79.6
Sometimes	37	18.9
Not Often	3	1.5
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

As shown in table 9, 156(79.6%) of the respondents indicated they always wash their hands for at least 20 seconds. 37(18.9%) sometimes wash their hands whilst 3(1.5%) not often.

From figure 6, majority of the respondents, 177(90.3%) indicated the use disposable gloves when handling soiled linen and body fluids or items whilst 19(9.7%) do not use disposable gloves.

Figure 6: Usage of Disposable Gloves

Table 10: Covering nose/mouth with tissue when coughing and sneezing

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Always	162	82.7
Sometimes	31	15.8
Seldom	3	1.5
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Majority of the respondents, 162(82.7%) always cover their nose and mouth with tissue when coughing or sneezing, 31(15.8%) sometimes cover their nose and mouth whilst 3(1.5%) seldom cover their nose and mouth when sneezing or coughing with tissue. This is represented in table 10.

Table 11: Seating arrangements made to ensure more distancing

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Always	117	59.7
Sometimes	64	32.7
Seldom	4	2.0
Not Often	11	5.6
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

More than half, 117(59.7%) of the respondents noted that seating arrangements are always made to ensure distancing, 64(32.7%) indicated sometimes, 11(5.6%) stated not often whilst

4(2%) seldom arrange seating to ensure distancing as shown in table 11.

Less than half of the respondents, 93(47.4%) indicated that all patients are made to wear facemask always, 45(23%) indicated it is done sometimes, 33(16.8%) indicated seldom whilst 25(12.8%) indicate all patients do not often wear facemask before they are being attended to. This is depicted in figure 7.

Figure 7: All patients are made to Wear Face mask

Table 12: I give patient education at work

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Always	94	48.0
Sometimes	84	43.0
Seldom	12	6.1
Not Often	6	3.1
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

From table 12, patient education is always done by 94(48%) of the respondents, 84(43%) sometimes give patient education at work, 12(6.1%) seldom give patient education whilst 6(3.1%) not often give patient education at work.

Table 13: I wear facemask to protect myself

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Always	178	90.8
Sometimes	15	7.7
Seldom	3	1.5
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Majority of the respondents, 178(90.8%) always wear face mask to protect themselves, 15(7.7%) sometimes wear facemask to protect themselves and 3(1.5%) seldom wear face mask to protect them. This is shown in table 13.

Table 14: I dust surfaces and door handles regularly

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Always	123	62.8
Sometimes	58	29.6
Seldom	6	3.1
Not Often	9	4.6
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

I dust surfaces and door handles regularly was indicated by 123(62.8%), 58(29.6%) sometimes dust surfaces and door handles, 6(4.6%) not often dust surfaces and door handles whilst 6(3.1%) seldom dust surfaces and door handles as depicted in table 14.

Table 15: I reuse facemask

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Always	55	28.1
Sometimes	87	44.4
Seldom	15	7.7
Not Often	39	19.9
Total	196	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2020

87(44.4%) of the respondents indicated they sometimes reuse facemask, 55(28.1%) always reuse facemask, 39(9.9%) not often reuse facemask and 15(7.47%) seldom reuse facemask. This is shown in table 15.

Majority of the respondents, 153(78.1%) always avoid hand shaking of their colleagues and friends, 36(18.4%) sometimes avoid hand shaking of their colleagues whilst 7(3.6%) seldom avoid handshaking of their colleagues and friends as shown in figure 8.

Figure 8: I avoid hand shaking of colleagues and friends

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

5.1 Bio-Demographic Data

Results from the study showed close to half of the respondents are young professionals, 47.5% (20-30 years and 46.4% (31-40years). This means that working populace at the hospitals are of youthful age. Most of the respondents (60.2%) were males with majority (63.8%) working at the Tamale Teaching Hospital. This finding is probable because the number of nurse and midwifery specialties in the Tamale Teaching Hospital outnumbers that of the Tamale Central hospital which is a primary health care facility. Cumulatively, more than half worked at the medical wards with majority being general nurses (65.8%) and a good number attaining the rank of enrolled nurse. The working experience of the respondents for majority of them was between 1-5years (51.1%). Most respondents (65.8%) are single and has diploma in nursing/midwifery (52%). These findings are consistent with Erfani et al, (2020) study which noted that different age group, level of education, and marital status of participants influences their level of knowledge and practices. Saqlain et al, (2020) also found participants demonstrated good practices associated with working experience, age and gender.

5.2 Knowledge Level of Respondents Regarding Coronavirus (SARS-CoV 2)

In assessing the level of knowledge of respondents, majority 95(48.5%) knew COVID-19 was first identified and made to the airwaves in November and December, 2019 and was isolated and named by WHO in January 2020 where it was declared a medical emergency in February 2020 and a global pandemic in March, 2020. This confirms the WHO (2020) report that declared coronavirus as a medical emergency.

Majority of the respondents, 110(56.1%) had their sources of coronavirus information through television. Other sources of information were radio, 16(8.2%), social media 10(5.1%), reports from the GHS/MoH as well as from colleagues. This finding is consistent with Nemati et al, (2020) study results that showed that most of the nurses had their sources of information from the WHO's website and Iran's MoH regular updates from the media and other social applications.

The cause of COVID-19 was correctly identified to be from SARS-CoV 2 170(86.7%). All of the respondents 196(100%) noted that the virus can be spread from human to human and health workers with nurses being at a higher risk of getting infected. Difficulty in breathing, sore throat, fever, coughing and runny nose are the possible symptoms of COVID-19 with the virus having an incubation period between 2 to 14 days with infected persons above 60 years at risk of complications. This confirms Al-Hazmi et al, (2018) study result that identified fever and difficulty breathing as symptoms. Similarly, the study found persons with comorbidities 179(91.3%) such as chronic heart problems, hypertension, diabetes and others to have a high mortality rate. This confirms Asaad et al, (2020) finding where majority of the participants knew the causative organism of the disease and the persons with higher risk of getting complications. The results however contradicts the finding that indicated few participants were knowledgeable regarding the incubation period (Asaad et al, 2020).

Most of the respondents knew there was neither vaccine nor specific treatment regimen for COVID-19. Al-Hazmi et al., (2018) noted that, there has not been any specific drug regimen for the management of MERS, SARS and Covid-19 therefore; utilizing protocols that will prevent transmission of the infection is very relevant. Respondents also knew that transmission of the infection could be through close contact, overcrowded areas and touching or handling of infected surfaces/items 196(100%). In addition, 175(89.3%) of the respondents indicated quarantining or isolation of patients is used in the management of COVID-19 with more than half, 124(63.3%) stating that persons who do not exhibit symptoms cannot transmit the virus. Respondents also stated as part of the prevention protocols wearing of face mask and regular hand washing 192(98%). This is in tandem with the

study by Erfani et al, (2020) which depicted a high score in the knowledge level on the characteristics of the disease, persons or groups who are at a higher risk and how the disease is transmitted. The findings showed different age groups, the level of education of participants, age and their marital status influenced the level of knowledge.

5.3 Attitudes toward Covid-19 Prevention

Respondents demonstrated good attitude generally towards the prevention of COVID 19. All the respondents, 196(100%) indicated their readiness to attend COVID-19 training programs, they were confident in their ability to fight against COVID-19 and were ready to give education on COVID-19. Majority 171(87.2%) feared their relatives may get infected, 193(98.5%) were willing to be quarantined should they contract the disease, use their working experience in the area of COVID-19 prevention and the usage of preventive guidelines designed by health agencies. This contradicts the finding of Shi et al, (2020) who found in their study that the level of confidence of the psychiatrist in protecting themselves and others was higher than that of the nurses even though they showed their readiness to help and support and care for patients with COVID-19. The results however agreed with Giao et al, (2020) study findings which reported healthcare workers also showed concern about themselves and their relatives getting infected. The participants showed their readiness to be quarantined should any of them contract COVID-19. They however, noted that the best method of prevention is regular hand hygiene (Giao et al, 2020).

Furthermore, 144(73.5%) of the respondents noted that increased workload affects their work attitude towards COVID-19, 147(75%) don PPE properly before they attend to patients and 174(88.8%) of the respondents are self-motivated to go to work every day in this pandemic. It is a worrying situation that 49(25%) of the nurses unable to don PPE properly. This could predispose them to getting infected.

5.4 Practices towards COVID-19 Prevention

The prevention practices level of the respondents has been noted to be good. Majority of the respondents 156(79.6%) always wash their hands for at least 20 seconds, 177(90.3%) always use disposable gloves when handling soiled linen and body fluids or items, 162(82.7%) always cover their nose and mouth with tissue when coughing or sneezing, more than half, 117(59.7%) make

seating arrangements in a manner that there is always distancing. These are consistent with the WHO (2020) general rule and practice in the prevention of the spread of COVID-19 which emphasize on frequent washing of hands using soap under running water for at least 20-40 seconds, the use of hand-rubs made from alcohol based agents in the absence of items needed to wash hands and observing a respectable distance, covering of the mouth and nose when coughing or sneezing and properly disposing off used tissues.

To involve patients in the prevention practices, 93(47.4%) make all patients wear facemask always before they are cared for, patient education is always done by 94(48%) of the respondents and majority of the respondents, 178(90.8%) always wear face mask to protect themselves. Dusting of surfaces and door handles regularly was indicated by 123(62.8%), 87(44.4%) of the respondents sometimes reuse facemask whilst majority 153(78.1%) always avoid hand shaking of their colleagues and friends. Kumar et al, (2020) in their study revealed the nurses mostly do not take off their face mask when they need to speak to a patient. They do not also reuse the surgical mask; however, they wear a mask when they move within or around the hospital and at public places to prevent them from contacting the infection. Lihua et al, (2020) also recommended in their study that there is the need to encourage regular disinfection of surfaces and handles with alcohol or chlorine and regular handwashing before and after eating.

5.5 Limitations of the Study

The study results cannot be generalized since it utilized only two hospitals in the Tamale Metropolis. The study did not also report on real life experiences with the use of self-administered questionnaire. The absence of the researcher at the point of completing the questions by respondents did not offer adequate room to offer more clarifications on some of the questions where necessary to the respondents. This has a potential to skew the responses. The study did not also observe the proper hand washing practices, disposal of used items and usage of the facemask.

6. SUMMARY

The coronavirus pandemic that engulfed the world continues to bring health care facilities and personnel including nurses to their knees. Both human and material resources are overburdened,

cost of personal protective equipment have soared up amidst high demand.

Nevertheless, nurses continue to play the frontline role to aid in dealing with the pandemic. This exposes them to contracting the virus therefore making it essential for nurses to acquaint themselves with high level of knowledge and prevention practices to stay safe to continue to render care to patients.

The study explored the nurses' knowledge, attitude and practices regarding the prevention of coronavirus (COVI-19). A quantitative descriptive study design was used and data were collected using a self-administered questionnaires and analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. Valuable methods of data collection like observation of actual practices and document review were not used because of limited time for the study. The study found high level of knowledge, good attitude and practices to the prevention of COVID-19 infection.

7. CONCLUSION

Based on the study findings, it can be concluded that the nurses had adequate knowledge regarding coronavirus (SARS-CoV 2). The attitude of the nurses can generally be considered to be good with good prevention practices that can be associated with their educational qualification, working experience and motivational levels.

8. NURSING IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The implication of this study on nursing practice is that, the level of knowledge, attitude and prevention practices of the nurses may be hindered. This is because, there has not been consistent supply of PPEs for use at the various health facilities making nurses adamant in putting in their best.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the study findings, it is recommended that a policy be developed to build the capacity for nurses caring for patients infected with COVID-19 and encouraging nurses to study other relevant guidelines. This should include periodic staff training, translation of research findings into practice and retaining those trained on units where they can perform effectively without rotating them to inappropriate units.

A study involving more than one hospital is recommended to gain more insight on the

knowledge, attitude and practices of nurses regarding prevention of COVID-19.

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